

ISic4098

I.Sicily inscription 4098

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

perhaps excavations of E. piraino di Mandralisca in contr. Diana

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost, Seen by Libertini in the Museo Mandralisca at Cefalu pre-1921

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334631

1. [— — —]ΔPONI [— — —] ²⁷[Αν]δρόνι[κος](?)²⁷

2. [— — —]ANIIOC [— — —]

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 334631

Bibliography

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Libertini, G 1921. Le isole eolie nell'antichità greca e romana. Ricerche storiche

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